

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

Annual Report
2000 - 2001

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THE COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES (CLIR) grew out of the 1997 merger of the Commission on Preservation and Access (CPA) and the Council on Library Resources (CLR). Over the years, CPA and CLR, in partnership with libraries, archives, and other information providers, advocated collaborative approaches to preserving the nation's intellectual heritage and strengthening the many components of its information system. CLIR was founded to continue this tradition of support for a national information system and a seamless web of information resources, of which all libraries and archives are a part.

The convening role is central to CLIR's mission. CLIR brings together experts from around the country and around the world and asks them to turn their intelligence to the problems that libraries, archives, and information organizations face as they integrate digital resources and services into their well-established print-based environments.

CLIR urges individuals to look beyond the immediate challenges and imagine the most desirable outcomes for the users of libraries and archives—to be rigorously practical and to dream.

Quotation excerpts in cover image are from *Science and the Common Understanding* by Robert Oppenheimer (Simon and Schuster 1954). The complete quotation is:

The open society, the unrestricted access to knowledge, the unplanned and uninhibited association of men for its furtherance—these are what make a vast, complex, ever growing, ever changing, ever more specialized and expert technological world, nevertheless a world of human community.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

ANNUAL REPORT 2000-2001

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LETTER FROM THE CHAIRMAN

Stanley Chodorow
Chairman

One of the great pleasures of chairing the Board of CLIR is having the opportunity to work with the committed and visionary people who serve on it. CLIR's staff can rely on the Board for guidance in developing and carrying out the organization's program. The agendas of Board meetings focus on issues that the staff and members of the Board expect to become important for institutions and individuals responsible for managing information and information systems.

The composition of CLIR's Board changes each year through the normal rotation of members' terms. While this change ensures the continual renewal of the Board, it also means that we lose the experience and wisdom of members who have served CLIR for years. In 2001, we lost more experience than usual because of the evolution of CLIR's Board as the successor of the Boards of the Council on Library Resources and the Commission on Preservation and Access. I want to use this opportunity to recognize those who stepped down this year.

Betty Bengtson left the CLIR Board when she retired from her position as library director at the University of Washington. We will miss Betty for her understanding of the research library community and for her commitment to preservation.

Virginia Betancourt, who joined the CLIR Board while she was director of the National Library of Venezuela, completed her term. Virginia is now devoting her energy and talent to the Fundacion Romulo Betancourt. We are especially grateful for the expert advice she offered on matters related to CLIR's international work.

Christine Borgman, professor of information studies at the University of California at Los Angeles, gave the Board knowledge of the information science research community. She also made an important contribution through her connection to the National Science Foundation's digital library initiatives.

Robert Bovenschulte, director of publications at the American Chemical Society, joined the CLIR Board as a representative from the publishing community, but he also contributed business acumen, knowledge of the technological changes in publishing, and plain good sense to the Board's deliberations.

David B. Gracy II, a faculty member at the University of Texas, provided strong representation of the archival community. David made archives and archival issues a part of every CLIR project. In addition, as secretary of the Board, he introduced us to proper archival procedures.

Marilyn Gell Mason joined the CLIR Board while she was director of the Cleveland Public Library, and she continued to represent the interests and concerns of public libraries after she left that position to become an adviser to OCLC. Marilyn also served as vice chair of the Board.

We are delighted to welcome four new members to the Board.

Francis X. Blouin, director of the Bentley Historical Library at the University of Michigan, brings the perspective of an archivist to the Board. Before accepting the invitation to serve on the CLIR Board, he had already contributed significantly to CLIR's work as a member of its Task Force on the Role of the Artifact.

Paula Kaufman, university librarian at the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, comes to the CLIR Board with broad professional experience and a history of service on numerous boards, including the Research Libraries Group, SOLINET, the Society for Scholarly Publishing, and the Association for Research Libraries, of which she is president-elect.

Susan Kent, who heads the Los Angeles Public Library, has had a distinguished career in the world of public libraries. She has been recognized nationally and internationally for her accomplishments and leadership.

Finally, Celia Ribeiro Zaher, director of the National Library Foundation of the Ministry of Culture in Brazil, contributes to the Board's international perspective and gives us particularly valuable views on Latin America.

The diverse professional backgrounds of the CLIR Board members mirror the expanding range of communities with which CLIR has become connected. The success of CLIR's work today depends on cooperation with industry, publishers, and museums, as well as with our traditional partners in universities and libraries.

As the CLIR Board and staff look to the future and make decisions about new initiatives and directions, we will welcome new Board members with diverse experience and knowledge who can assist us with planning those activities.

Stanley Chodorow
Chairman of the Board

MESSAGE FROM THE PRESIDENT

Deanna B. Marcum
President

We opened last year's annual report with a question: What is a library? Today, the answer to that question is more elusive than ever. In 2001, the shape and form of the library in the digital age continued to be at the center of our work. We challenged our constituents to imagine a library that does not demand that the user be physically present to take advantage of its services. For years, the CLIR staff, like our colleagues across the nation and the world, has painted some version of this dream for faculty, students, and the public. We have pointed to the many advantages of computer networks for delivering information to people anytime, anywhere. But moving from a physically bounded space containing collections that have been built in response to local demands is harder than most librarians care to admit. Libraries are serving audiences unknown to them, and it is difficult to satiate the appetite of new patrons for electronic resources.

As librarians think about those users who are not part of their traditional constituencies, they ask a fundamental and thought-provoking question: Whom do we serve, and exactly what do we offer them? Local libraries have unique cultures. The librarians who manage them have worked hard to learn their users' preferences, special needs, and requirements. Collections have been built with care and attention that bespeak the close connections that exist between the library and those who depend upon it. Adding a layer of users we do not know—and probably will never know—presents interesting questions about the library's roles and responsibilities.

It would be relatively simple to serve new audiences if we could think of digital collections merely as additions to the print and audiovisual collections that are described in our online catalogs. If that were the case, users could simply consult these catalogs for the information they need. But it is not that simple. In addition to placing collections online, librarians must consider the services that will accompany those digital collections.

Most librarians continue to think of the library as the place it has been for the past hundred years or so—an authoritative center for information resources. However, digital-era patrons, particularly students, think of the library in different terms and have different expectations. Increasingly, we hear reports from faculty members that their students are interested only in digital resources. Students cite convenience, as well as the ability to

retrieve information on their own rather than to rely on a librarian, as key advantages of digitization. Faculty members are trying hard to persuade their students that they must go beyond the computer screen to find all of the materials they need for in-depth study and research. Nonetheless, when we pay close attention to the use patterns of students and patrons in a variety of types of institutions, it becomes clear that the need for an authoritative physical institution is indeed decreasing.

This period of transition from a purely physical manifestation of the library to the hybrid condition of print and electronic resources and eventually, we assume, to a largely digital collection, requires libraries to assess their ability to go beyond the physical building and mediated services to the more abstract virtual library—a library that will not be recognized as a “place” in the traditional sense of the word. While those of us who know the great value of curated print collections would like to share our understanding with our users, we are compelled to recognize that new generations of information seekers place a higher value on convenience and speed than on carefully assembled and authoritative print collections.

Amidst these rapid changes, there is one constant. It is the need for access to high-quality research materials. Faculty members need the support of librarians in finding new ways to make connections between the user and the materials that will make possible intelligent inquiry and the creation of new knowledge. How will librarians serve their traditional roles in this new environment? Can the library find ways to deliver high-quality digital information such that it meets users’ needs for immediacy and convenience?

Role of Digitized Collections

Recognizing that students, as well as many faculty members, are more interested in resources that can be found on the Web than they are in traditional print resources, some librarians are establishing production-level digitization laboratories. Others are developing portals that will lead information seekers to Web sites of curated resources. Most librarians and archivists are convinced that the most important action they can take is to digitize as many of their research collections as possible or to lead their users to digital collections of other institutions. Funding agencies have helped fuel the digitization activities in libraries and archives, and the results are encouraging. The Library of Congress (LC), by digitizing its own collections and providing access to those of others, has made available 7 million images of special collections materials relating to American history. With help from private foundations and government agencies, notably the Institute of Museum and Library Services, many academic and public libraries, historical societies, archives, and museums have selected

the special collections materials most likely to be of interest to a broader public and have converted them to digital form.

This interest in digitization has had many positive results. Chief among them is a growing interest among cultural institutions in working together to identify and digitize important collections. At the same time, new problems have emerged. For example, many of these special collections materials have not been cataloged. When these images are added to the Web, only brief descriptions accompany them. When a user is searching the Web, what are the chances that he or she will find all the related materials from many different institutions when there are no standards for description?

CLIR's Task Force on the Role of the Artifact in Library Collections has risen to the challenge of offering guidance to librarians and archivists on preserving artifactual collections of research value. The task force, made up primarily of scholars, acknowledged that many resources must be in digital form for purposes of access, but it also urged collections stewards to pay special attention to preserving certain types of artifacts that will be necessary for historical research. Finding that balance between more digital access and long-term preservation of artifactual special collections will be a high priority for CLIR in the coming months.

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) has concentrated on defining the infrastructure that must be in place if libraries are to harness information technology effectively. In response to an immediate need, DLF has described the requirements for a service that registers the existence of persistent digitally reformatted book and serial publications.

In addition to making the case for the development of a registry service, the DLF developed functional requirements for such a service. Although the registry service is not intended to be exclusive (it will record information about the large and valuable legacy of digitized books and serials) it does set forth minimum characteristics that might be expected of a faithful digital reproduction. DLF itself does not expect to establish this service, but it is engaged in identifying a service organization that is capable of assuming this responsibility.

Preservation in the Digital World

CLIR has always had a strong interest in preservation issues, but the increase in electronic resources intensifies the need to resolve questions about the longevity of digital materials. In 1996, CLIR and the Research Libraries Group issued a seminal report entitled *Preserving Digital Information*. Much progress has been made since this document was published, but a preservation infrastructure for digital information is not yet in place.

When the U.S. Congress announced in late 2000 that it would add \$100 million to the LC budget to develop a national infrastructure for preserving digital information, the LC turned to CLIR for assistance in developing the plan for such an infrastructure. Although it is unusual for CLIR to be engaged directly in a particular library's planning project, we believe that this is a unique opportunity to work with another leadership organization engaged in conceptualizing some of the infrastructural elements that must be in place in the new environment. In some respects, CLIR's role in this effort is an extension of one that it has assumed successfully in the past, namely, to convene disparate parties who have a specific interest in an issue. The outcome of the national plan for the preservation of digital information is enormously important, and CLIR is pleased to play a role in articulating the plan.

CLIR Looks to the Future

CLIR is not immune to the external forces that shape contemporary libraries and archives. As we become involved in efforts to reconceptualize library services in the digital environment, we are compelled to consider changes in our own role and mission. We decided that our thinking about changes that must be made should begin at home. For this reason, we commissioned a survey of how our sponsors, as well as organizations we would like to have as sponsors, perceive the value of CLIR's work.

This is the first such analysis that CLIR has ever attempted. To carry it out, we contracted with The Communications Office, Inc., to ask our sponsoring and other colleagues to reflect on the extent to which CLIR's programs and publications meet their needs.

The results, while gratifying on one level, indicate that better understanding of CLIR's agenda is needed. Our program staff has begun a series of focused sessions to articulate our vision and mission. As we imagine the changes that libraries, archives, museums, and other cultural organizations will experience as they find their proper roles in the digital world, how do we assist them? We expect to have a more specific answer to this question in the next several months.

A Word of Thanks

The generous support of more than 175 institutions, private foundations, and individual donors makes our work possible. We are privileged to work with these partners in reshaping information services for the future.

CLIR's traditional institutional sponsors—research libraries and liberal arts college libraries—have been unflinching in their support. In addition, three comprehensive university members joined the rank of sponsor this

year. In 2001, the number of CLIR sponsors grew from 145 to 161, an increase of 11 percent. The DLF added one member, the University of Washington, to bring its membership to 26 institutional participants.

The general support for CLIR provided by The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation and the William and Flora Hewlett Foundation has been invaluable. This type of support gives us the flexibility to move quickly into areas that need attention or to focus deeply on a problem that requires more staff power.

Project funding provided by The Atlantic Philanthropies, the Gladys Krieble Delmas Foundation, Documentation Abstracts, Inc., the Henry Luce Foundation, the Institute of Museum and Library Services, the H. W. Wilson Foundation, and the Robert W. Woodruff Foundation allowed us to maintain important programs such as the Frye Leadership Institute and to begin new projects, such as a communications program aimed at policy makers in higher education.

The financial investment that sponsors and funding agencies have made in CLIR has given our staff a stable foundation. The creativity and dedication of the staff are awe-inspiring, and their contributions multiply each year as they make more connections with other organizations and find ways to mesh our agenda with those of other organizations. CLIR's standards of excellence begin with the staff.

This year, CLIR program staff welcomed two new members. Anne Kenney joined us in September 2000 as a half-time director of programs. She also works half-time for Cornell University Libraries. Jerry George, formerly of the National Archives and Records Administration, joined CLIR as special projects associate. We bid a reluctant farewell to Ann Marie Parsons, a student in The Catholic University of America's School of Library and Information Science, who left CLIR in May after completing her master's degree internship.

It is a great pleasure to work with staff of such extraordinary talent and commitment. It is equally rewarding to work with the CLIR Board—16 individuals from different perspectives who set the tone and standards for our organization. I consider myself fortunate to work on important problems confronting information organizations with our staff, Board, partner organizations, and funding agencies and sponsors. I am deeply grateful for their contributions and for the trust they have placed in me.

*Deanna B. Marcum
President*

September 30, 2001

THE PROGRAMS

RESOURCES FOR SCHOLARSHIP

Scholarship is dynamic; research trends are emerging that could not have been predicted even a decade ago. Digital technology is transforming scholarship, and new methods of inquiry, scholarly communication, and teaching are accelerating the rate of change in research trends. The increase in use of electronic sources such as e-journals and digitized collections is, however, accompanied by a continued reliance on original sources for historical research. Seeing these trends and anticipating the pressures that they will bring to libraries and archives, CLIR has brought together librarians and scholars in several programs to assess current and future needs both for electronic access to information and for access to original collections in all genres and formats.

The Task Force on the Artifact in Library Collections

In 2001, a task force of 15 scholars, librarians, and archivists, assembled by CLIR in 1999 to investigate the demands for original source materials, produced its draft report, *The Evidence in Hand: Report of the Task Force on the Artifact in Library Collections*. The task force engaged the research community in six public reviews of its findings and recommendations and posted the draft report on CLIR's Web site for public comment. The chief findings of the report—that scholarship will continue to interrogate original sources for many reasons, and that the broadest-possible access to unformatted sources therefore best serves scholarship—were by no means controversial. But the breadth of sources identified—from traditional print collections to recorded sound, broadcast media, moving and still images, and all manner of digital information—greatly expanded the universe of materials that libraries, as well as archives, historical museums, and museums, should be collecting and preserving.

Acknowledging that funds for preservation are limited, the task force proposed a number of approaches. Many rely on cooperation among institutions to reduce unnecessary duplication of preservation responsibilities and engender cost efficiencies that will ensure the appropriate types of redundancies through distributed repositories of artifactual collections and, when possible, broadened access to digital and other surrogates.

The public reviews confirmed that the task force was addressing issues deemed critical by the research community. The section on digital resources and the novel, often perplexing, responsibilities that face librarians and scholars when creating and using digital sources drew special interest. The task force's recommendations to ensure the creation of preservable digital objects while preserving the sources for digitized materials have already influenced developments in the Digital Library Federation libraries and their many partners.

Creating a Test Database for Digital Visual Resources

Computer searching is at its best when it works with standard, replicable characters, such as numbers and letters of the alphabet. But what are the defining components of an image? The quest to create reliable means for searching databases of images has given rise to a range of solutions that focus either on the development of appropriate descriptive metadata or on the creation of effective visual searching software (e.g., content-based image retrieval). Nonetheless, creating a means by which generic images can be searched broadly remains an elusive goal.

CLIR and the Coalition for Networked Information (CNI) are investigating the value and feasibility of developing a test database for digital visual resources. Such a database could serve as a means of measuring the capabilities of various technical applications for creating, managing, and exploiting digital image content.

Project Director Clifford Lynch is preparing scenarios depicting two approaches to developing the database. In the first approach, the database would be designed to support fundamental long-term research into image-retrieval techniques. This would be most useful to computer science researchers interested in content-based retrieval.

In the second approach, the database would be designed to support the assessment of metadata for retrieving and using image files. Special emphasis would be placed on understanding the costs and benefits of investing in metadata creation. This approach would require research into how users are querying image databases. Two test collections would be used in this approach: one in art and another in history or historic photographs. For both types of collections, metadata would be created that could support multidisciplinary use.

Jennifer Trant will serve as a consultant on this project. Working from these two scenarios, she will develop a report on the resource implications and processes necessary to assemble content and metadata. Her report and the scenarios will be circulated for comment. CLIR will issue a final report on these proposals in early 2002.

PRESERVATION AWARENESS

Recorded Sound in Peril

Recorded sound exists on a variety of fragile media—wax cylinders, cassette tapes, lacquer disks—that pose urgent physical preservation problems. The challenges to preserving recorded sound collections, however, extend far beyond the fragility of formats. The media depend on playback hardware that goes quickly out of use. Basic intellectual controls over these collections, including essential inventory control and cataloging records, are lacking. The complex network of intellectual property rights inherent in recorded performances make identifying the copyright status of a work difficult and, at times, impossible. Finally, there is no funding to address these problems systematically.

This year, CLIR worked with the American Folklore Society and the American Folklife Center at the Library of Congress to raise awareness of these problems and to develop an agenda for preserving sound collections. In December 2000, the three organizations convened a meeting to examine in depth the problems facing one set of recordings: folk heritage. The meeting, *Folk Heritage Collections in Crisis*, brought together folklorists, technologists, preservation experts, librarians and archivists, recording company executives, and intellectual property lawyers to describe the current state of these collections, to develop strategies for solving problems shared by so many distinct communities, and to form working groups that would take next steps. CLIR published a report of the discussions and recommendations in May 2001.

The State of Preservation Programs in American College and Research Libraries

There is an urgent need to reformulate the preservation agenda in light of a changing information environment. But it is nearly impossible to frame a new agenda without understanding what is happening now. In January 2001, CLIR convened a planning group to consider the scope and duration of a major study on preservation as outlined in a white paper prepared by CLIR's staff. Participants agreed there was a need to reevaluate our underlying assumptions and called for a national study of the state of preservation across the full spectrum of college and research libraries.

In fall 2001, CLIR will initiate such a study, with the assistance of the Association of Research Libraries, the University Libraries Group, and the Regional Alliance for Preservation, and with representation from the Oberlin Group, land-grant institutions, preservation educators, and the American Library Association. As part of the study, CLIR will also begin working with the library community to develop a long-term preservation agenda.

DIGITAL LIBRARIES

CLIR is committed to fostering the development of digital libraries as a resource for research and learning. The aim is to help policy makers, funding organizations, and academic leaders understand the social and institutional investments in information technology that are needed to manage and provide access to our scholarly and cultural heritage.

The Digital Library Federation (DLF) is the primary manifestation of CLIR's interest in digital libraries. Operating under CLIR's auspices, the DLF is a consortium of 26 research libraries that are pioneering the use of electronic-information technologies as a means of extending their collections and services. Through its members, the DLF provides leadership for libraries by

- identifying standards and best practices for digital collections and network access
- coordinating leading-edge research and development in libraries' use of electronic information technology
- helping start needed projects and services that libraries cannot develop individually

Two years ago, the DLF broadened its program to six areas: architectures and technologies, collection development, digital preservation, standards and best practices, use and user support, and roles and responsibilities of the digital library. This year, the DLF continued its efforts in these areas while making progress in fulfilling three higher-level purposes, notably

- specifying the infrastructures that must be in place for libraries to harness information technology to support their stewardship of scholarly and cultural information
- pooling efforts in the conduct of essential research
- promoting adoption of standards and practices that support libraries in developing high-quality, interoperable, and persistent online collections and services

Highlights from our progress in fulfilling these higher-level aims follow.

Specifying Infrastructure

Acting as a catalyst, the DLF facilitates the development of infrastructural organization and services that are commonly required by digital libraries but are beyond their independent means.

■ **ArtSTOR.** Led by Distinguished Fellow Max Marmor of Yale University, the DLF created a prototype for the organizational, business, and

technical aspects of an image distribution service. This year, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation drew on the DLF's work to formulate and launch ArtSTOR, "an independent not-for-profit organization that will develop, 'store,' and distribute electronically digital images and related scholarly materials for the study of art, architecture, and other fields in the humanities." ArtSTOR marks a major advance in the development and dissemination of visual image resources that support research and teaching. It has also taken over the DLF's work on a shared catalog tool for visual resources.

■ **Open Archives Initiative.** Working with CNI, the DLF supported the Open Archives Initiative (OAI), which aims to develop and promote interoperability standards to facilitate the efficient dissemination of information content. In doing so, it helped develop and sustain a protocol upon which the next generation of scholarly Internet portal services is likely to be built. The OAI is being adopted enthusiastically in the United States and abroad. Internet services that use it are attracting investment from The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, the National Science Foundation, and the European Union. In addition, the DLF is helping facilitate the development of some such services. Several DLF members, including Cornell, Emory, Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, and Michigan, are helping develop innovative portal services. Twelve DLF members have agreed to contribute to such services the metadata from more than 50 collections representing millions of objects. Metadata from several of these collections are already available from the Library of Congress, the University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, the University of Pennsylvania, and the University of Tennessee at Knoxville.

■ **E-Journals Repository.** Building on work conducted by CLIR, DLF, and CNI on the minimum criteria that libraries and publishers may require of an electronic-journal repository, The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation established an e-journal archiving program and funded seven institutions to plan the development of such repositories. With this program, libraries and publishers take a significant step forward in addressing their shared preservation concerns. The DLF supports the program by hosting its Web pages, reporting its progress to the broader community, and encouraging cross-fertilization among its funded participants. Six DLF members are involved in the program: Cornell University, Harvard University, the New York Public Library, the University of Pennsylvania, Stanford University, and Yale University.

Research

Pooling expertise at individual digital libraries, the DLF has conducted significant new research into strategic, technical, organizational, and other problem areas.

■ **Sustainable Digital Collections.** This year, the DLF completed three studies that report strategies for developing sustainable digital collections. Based on a survey of practice at leading research libraries, the studies recommend strategies for developing collections from commercially supplied electronic content (Timothy Jewell, University of Washington), digitally reformatted content (Abby Smith, CLIR), and links to third-party public domain Internet content (Louis Pitschmann, University of Wisconsin).

■ **Use of Online Services and Collections.** Led by Distinguished Fellow Denise Troll, the DLF completed a survey of how leading research libraries assess the use of online collections and services. The survey, when published, will provide a comprehensive overview and critical assessment of the newest evaluation methods and how digital libraries can use them. The DLF also completed a member survey that identifies the institutional contexts in which digital libraries are being developed. By documenting the very different paths along which digital libraries evolve and the different ways in which they organize and fund themselves, the survey will inform strategic planning and decision making within digital libraries, provide benchmarks for assessing digital library development, and identify emerging library roles.

Standards and Best Practices

Leveraging its members' collective influence, the DLF seeks to identify, endorse, and encourage adoption of those standards and practices that support the development of persistent and interoperable online collections and services.

This year, the DLF endorsed a number of standards and best practices while launching new work in other directions. Among the practices it endorsed is LibLicense, a model license agreement for use by libraries and commercial publishers. The model license documents preferred and good practice and serves as a decision tool that is likely to save libraries time and money in negotiating contracts with commercial content providers.

The DLF initiated a process to develop a standard for representing structural, administrative, and technical metadata. Such a standard is a prerequisite for the construction of reliable and persistent distributed digital library collections. The DLF standard (known as METS for "metadata encoding and transmission standard") is in advanced development and available from the Library of Congress's Web site.

ECONOMICS OF INFORMATION

As the role of the library is redefined, economic issues take on even greater importance. Economics of information is a theme that cuts across all program activities at CLIR. The costs of library and information services and possible new economic models for those services underlie nearly every project in which CLIR engages.

Financial Models for Library Services

This year, CLIR Distinguished Fellow Angee Baker conducted a study of financial models of selected library services. The purpose of her study was to identify economic models that libraries might use to strengthen their positions in today's economy. Ms. Baker interviewed library directors and commercial information service providers to develop a survey instrument. Her search for economic models went beyond the library community to include commercial options. At the project's conclusion in December 2001, Ms. Baker will produce a report on the changes in collection development patterns in the digital environment. A key part of this document will be an analysis of the economic implications of those changes.

Building and Sustaining Digital Collections

In February, CLIR partnered with the National Initiative for a Networked Cultural Heritage (NINCH) to host a conference, *Building and Sustaining Digital Collections: Models for Libraries and Museums*. The meeting brought together library and museum executives, technologists, entrepreneurs, publishers, and legal experts to discuss how libraries and museums are building digital collections and what business models are available to sustain them. Participants heard presentations about six organizations, both nonprofit and for-profit, that are pioneering different approaches to the financial sustainability of online collections. Among the topics discussed were the circumstances under which a single organization can achieve its goals for online distribution of collections and services and when collaboration is necessary; how an institution can develop the technical, curatorial, legal, and administrative expertise for the variety of challenges that networked collections present; how market demands affect the core cultures of museums and libraries entering the online environment; and how business models can be developed for nonprofits. Participants identified a number of actions to be taken to address these concerns, and they are included in a report on the conference, which CLIR published in May.

The conference, funded by the Institute of Museum and Library Services, was a follow-up to *Collections, Content, and the Web*, which CLIR hosted with the Chicago Historical Society in October 1999.

LEADERSHIP

CLIR has a strong commitment to developing leaders for the information professions. All CLIR programs and publications are meant to provide new ideas, analyze and reinforce existing ideas, and educate individuals who aspire to leadership roles.

Frye Leadership Institute

The Frye Leadership Institute has quickly become one of the most visible and successful of CLIR's projects. Jointly sponsored by CLIR, EDUCAUSE, and Emory University, the Frye Institute brings together individuals from libraries, information technology divisions, and faculty departments in all types of academic institutions—from community colleges to large research universities.

The second Frye Institute was held at Emory University June 3–15, 2001. Fifty-three of the 175 applicants were selected for this residential program, which focuses on changes in higher education and on the role of information services in the academy. During the first week, presidents, provosts, business officers, and other administrative officers provided personal and often inspiring views of the contributions and challenges of higher education. In the second week, faculty conducted sessions on topics such as intellectual property and copyright, technological advances in teaching and research, scholarly communication, public policy, and personal leadership styles.

Participants were enthusiastic about the experience and gave the institute very high numerical ratings. In the narrative comments, many participants spoke of the transformational nature of the institute and the broadened understanding they had gained as a result of their participation in it.

Frye Institute participants,
June 2001

Patricia Battin, Brian Hawkins, Deanna Marcum, Billy Frye, Joan Gotwals, and Don Harris

Co-deans Deanna Marcum and Richard Detweiler present a certificate to Mark Colvson of Bryn Mawr College

The Robert W. Woodruff Foundation provides the primary support for the Frye Leadership Institute. Supplemental funding is provided by the Institute of Museum and Library Services and The Andrew W. Mellon Foundation. The Patricia Battin Scholarship Fund makes possible participation by individuals whose institutions cannot afford to support their attendance.

Academic Library Advisory Committee

The Academic Library Advisory Committee added one new member this year. Nicholas Burckel, director of Marquette University Libraries, joined the group as a representative of a comprehensive (non-Association of Research Libraries) university library.

The committee had identified three projects to receive priority this year: research on the outsourcing of library functions; the identification of issues in library and information resources that are of greatest interest to college and university presidents; and a study on the use of course management software and its impact on libraries.

Frye Institute Participants, Class of 2001

Karen Adams, Indiana University
Gary Allen, University of Missouri-Columbia
Martha Brogan, Indiana University
Thomas Brooks, Wheaton College
Madeline Carnevale, Mount Holyoke College
Robert Cartolano, Columbia University
Alan Cattier, Emory University
Mark Christel, Hope College
Kathy Christoph, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Beulah Clark, Baton Rouge Community College
W. Mark Colvson, Bryn Mawr College
Emory Craig, College of New Rochelle
Sarah Cron, Southeast Missouri State University
Erik Delfino, Library of Congress
John Ellis, University of Memphis
Linda Friend, Pennsylvania State University
Diane Graves, Hollins University
Samuel Hampton, Executive Leadership Foundation
Lynne Hamre, The College of St. Scholastica
Susan Hilton, University of Oregon
Hans Houshower, Bluffton College
John Howard, Harvard University
Barbara Kaplan, Sarah Lawrence College
Ruth Kifer, George Mason University
Elizabeth Kirk, Johns Hopkins University
Cynthia Krey, The College of St. Catherine
Dewitt Latimer, University of Tennessee
David Lewis, Indiana University, Purdue University,
Indianapolis
Dorothy Ohl Lewis, Iowa State University
Linda Matthews, Emory University
Ingrid Mauritzen, National Library of Norway
Susan Metros, University of Tennessee
Stephen Miller, University of Georgia
Lynn Kasner Morgan, Mount Sinai School of
Medicine
Kevin Morooney, Pennsylvania State University
John Ottenhoff, Alma College
Loretta O'Brien Parham, Hampton University
Gary Pratt, Northern Kentucky University
Carolyn Rawl, Auburn University Montgomery
Robyn Render, University of North Carolina
Michelle A-M Roberts, Delta State University
Michael Roy, Wesleyan University
James Schmidt, Western Illinois University
Harry Schulte, University of Texas at El Paso
Justin Sipher, State University of New York-Potsdam
David Sisk, Macalester College
Eugene Spencer, Bucknell University
Heather Stewart, Seton Hall University
Diane Tebbetts, University of New Hampshire
J. Rebecca Thompson, State University of New York-
Potsdam
Darlene Warren, University of Calgary
Linda Watson, University of Virginia Health System
Jian-Zhong Zhou, California State University-
Sacramento

A survey by Outsell, Inc., provided answers to the group's questions about libraries' success with outsourcing. After reviewing the results, the committee concluded that it would not be fruitful to develop case studies on this topic.

Committee Chairman David Cohen prepared a position paper on the relationship between the vendors of course management software systems and libraries. He noted that because the two groups rarely interact, students and researchers are often unaware of the wealth of information that exists but is not linked to a course Web site. After reviewing the results of in-depth interviews with vendors, the committee agreed to convene an invitational meeting in the fall of 2001 of library directors and vendors to discuss possible approaches that would allow greater representation of library materials through their systems.

CLIR's new publication series, *CLIRinghouse*, was created in response to recommendations by the Academic Library Committee and the CLIR Board. The publications staff spent several months this year developing ideas and testing them with our advisers. In addition, they worked with key administrators to determine the presentation format that would most likely be read.

Zipf Fellowship

The 2001 A. R. Zipf Fellowship in Information Management was awarded to Terence Kelly, a Ph.D. student in the Department of Computer Science at the University of Michigan. Mr. Kelly is the fifth recipient of the Zipf Fellowship. His research focuses on optimal resource allocation in hierarchical caching systems, especially Web caching. He has spoken and written extensively on this topic; his most recent article, "Optimal Web Cache Sizing: Scalable Methods for Exact Solutions," appeared in *Computer Communications* in February 2001.

The Zipf Fellowship is awarded annually to the graduate student in some field of information management or systems who best represents the ideals of Al Zipf, for whom the fellowship is named. Kent Smith, of the National Library of Medicine, chairs the selection committee. Other members are Christine Borgman, Martin Cummings, Billy Frye, and Rena Zipf.

Patricia Battin Scholarship

The second annual Patricia Battin Scholarship was awarded in June 2001 to Hans Houshower, director of technology at Bluffton College in Bluffton, Ohio. Established in 1999 by friends and family of Patricia Battin, the scholarship provides financial assistance for participants in the Frye Leadership Institute whose institutions cannot afford to support their attendance.

INTERNATIONAL DEVELOPMENTS

Web-Based Training Tutorials on Preservation and Conservation for Developing Countries

Librarians and archivists in many parts of the world lack the information they need to take basic preservation action. Language is sometimes a barrier to information access, but inappropriate content and poor distribution may be even bigger problems. The current preservation literature often focuses on highly specialized topics; it may recommend the use of technologies or materials that are costly or are not available everywhere. Little information has been designed and delivered with the needs of the developing world in mind.

With funding from the Henry Luce Foundation, CLIR this year held its first meeting to plan a series of Web-based tutorials on preservation and conservation for use in developing countries. The first tutorial is being designed for use in Southeast Asia. It will present 11 topics in three categories: management and planning, operations, and supporting the effort. It will include a self-assessment tool and a model for developing an action plan. Other features of the tutorial will be a glossary of technical terms, frequently asked questions, a vendor database, a forum, a calendar, and a search capability. Staff at cultural institutions in the targeted countries are being surveyed to identify special needs, levels of connectivity, and language skills. The Southeast Asian tutorial is scheduled for release in June 2002. CLIR expects to develop additional versions of the tutorial for other regions of the world.

Access to Manuscripts and Archives

The international community has shown great interest in the Encoded Archival Descriptors (EAD) that American archivists are developing to facilitate electronic access to manuscript and archival finding aids. CLIR, together with the German research consortium, Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft, sponsored the work of a group of German and American archivists to explore the use of EAD as a means of information exchange for German archives. This work has yielded important information about the flexibility of EAD in non-American contexts and how it can, or cannot, be used in different national archival traditions.

Partnership with Mortenson Center

CLIR is now an official partner of the Mortenson Center at the University of Illinois. The Mortenson Center, with endowment and foundation funding, has brought more than 500 librarians from 74 countries to take part in management training and development programs. CLIR will work with the Mortenson Center staff to tailor some portions of the Frye Leadership Institute to an international audience.

PUBLICATIONS

JULY 1, 2000 - JUNE 30, 2001

MONOGRAPHS AND REPORTS

Guides to Quality in Visual Resource Imaging. Web-based reference copublished by CLIR and Research Libraries Group. July 2000.

White Paper on Electronic Journal Usage Statistics. Judy Luther. October 2000.

Preservation Science Survey: An Overview of Recent Developments in Research on the Conservation of Selected Analog Library and Archival Materials. Henk J. Porck and René Teygeler. December 2000.

Folk Heritage Collections in Crisis. Council on Library and Information Resources. May 2001.

A Collaborative Approach to Collection Storage: The Five-College Library Depository. Willis E. Bridegam. June 2001

Building Sustainable Collections of Free Third-Party Web Resources. Louis A. Pitschmann. June 2001.

CLIR Annual Report, 1999–2000.

NEWSLETTERS

CLIR Issues, nos. 16–21.

ADVISORY GROUPS

Academic Library Advisory Committee

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Marquette University

David Cohen, *Chairman*
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Connie V. Dowell
San Diego State University

Michael Haeuser
Gustavus Adolphus College

Victoria L. Hanawalt
Reed College

CLIR Task Force on the Role of the Artifact in Library Collections

Francis X. Blouin
The University of Michigan

Bernard Cerquiglini
Institut national de la langue française

Rebecca S. Chopp
Emory University

Sheldon Hackney
University of Pennsylvania

Charles Méla
Université de Genève

Stephen G. Nichols, *Chairman*
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John Unsworth
University of Virginia

Nancy Vickers
Bryn Mawr College

Steve Wheatley
American Council of Learned Societies

Karin Wittenborg
University of Virginia

Pauline Yu
University of California, Los Angeles

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Mortenson Center for International Library Programs
University of Illinois

John Dean
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Alan Feinstein
The Toyota Foundation, Japan

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Emory University

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Thomas Leonard
University of California, Berkeley

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Coalition for Networked Information

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James Michalko*
Research Libraries Group

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Suzanne Thorin
Indiana University

Karin Trainer
Princeton University

William D. Walker
New York Public Library

Lizabeth Wilson
University of Washington

Karin Wittenborg
University of Virginia

* indicates DLF Allies

GRANTS AND CONTRACTS

ACTIVE IN FY 2001

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
American Folklore Society: Library of Congress Washington, DC	To support a conference on the preservation of folklore recordings	8/1/00	\$19,140
Baron, Robert A. Larchmont, NY	To oversee aspects of Academic Image Cooperative Project	11/29/99	\$33,600
Bridegam, Will Amherst, MA	To write a report on the Five College Library Depository	6/1/00	\$2,000
Brockman, Bill Urbana, IL	To write a report on humanities scholars' use of electronic resources	10/19/99	\$1,000
C. W. Shaver and Company, Inc. New York, NY	To conduct an assessment of CLIR	3/20/00	\$25,000
Carnegie Mellon University Pittsburgh, PA	To develop a prototype for the Academic Image Cooperative	10/26/99	\$155,000
Cohen, Elizabeth Los Angeles, CA	To write a paper for the conference, "Folklore Heritage Collections in Crisis"	7/1/00	\$2,000
Columbia University Press New York, NY	To convene focus sessions on use of electronic publications	5/18/99	\$20,000
Communications Office, Inc., The Alexandria, VA	To conduct an assessment of CLIR	10/17/00	\$25,000
Cornell University Computing Science Department Ithaca, NY	To support Cornell University's work on the Open Archives initiative (OAi)	11/13/00	\$84,800
Danielson, Virginia Cambridge, MA	To write a paper for the conference, "Folklore Heritage Collections in Crisis"	9/1/00	\$2,000
Informed Strategies Ardmore, PA	To write a report on electronic journal usage statistics	2/10/00	\$20,000
Irvine, Tatiana Chapel Hill, NC	To serve as recorder for the conference, "Folklore Heritage Collections in Crisis"	11/6/00	\$1,000
Jewell, Timothy Seattle, WA	To write a report for the conference, "Strategies for Developing Digital Collections"	7/10/00	\$4,000
Lawson, Roger C. Fredericksburg, VA	To serve as recorder for the conference, "Building and Sustaining Digital Collections: Models for Libraries and Museums"	12/27/00	\$2,000

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
Library of Congress Washington, DC	To partially support a symposium, "National Libraries of the World: Interpreting the Past, Shaping the Future"	4/11/00	\$10,000
Lougee, Wendy Ann Arbor, MI	To write a report on the changing role of libraries in the digital age	2/12/01	\$3,000
National Book Centre of Greece Athens, Greece	To translate preservation literature and organize preservation workshops	11/15/99	\$56,300
National Library of Australia Australia	To partially support a distributed digital preservation archive	2/28/01	\$5,000
Neustadt Center for the Benton Foundation Washington, DC	To produce a video on the role of the library in the community	12/14/98	\$88,000
Pitschmann, Louis Madison, WI	To write a report for the conference, "Strategies for Developing Digital Collections"	7/10/00	\$4,000
Queens Library Foundation Jamaica, NY	To partially support the "Second China-U.S. Conference on Libraries: Strategic Policy Directions for China-U.S. Library Cooperation"	1/16/01	\$5,000
Research Libraries Group Mountain View, CA	To support RLG DigiNews	5/19/99	\$19,668
Rodgers, David L. Ann Arbor, MI	To develop a business plan for the Frye Leadership Institute	1/15/01	\$10,000
Royal Library of the Netherlands The Netherlands	To conduct an international survey of significant developments in preservation science	11/9/99	\$12,000
Seeger, Anthony Los Angeles, CA	To write a paper for the conference, "Folklore Heritage Collections in Crisis"	6/29/00	\$2,000
Southeastern Library Network, Inc. Atlanta, GA	To support work on the competency guidelines for research librarians in the Southeast	7/28/00	\$20,000
Stanford University Libraries Stanford, CA	To conduct an in-depth study and survey of users of scholarly electronic journals	11/23/98	\$25,000
Stenlake, Rodney New Haven, CT	To analyze possible licensing arrangements among digital libraries	9/30/98	\$8,500

Recipient	Purpose	Authorized	Amount
University of California, Berkeley Berkeley, CA	To oversee translation into Spanish of texts on Encoded Archival Descriptors	12/20/99	\$10,000
University of California, Los Angeles Graduate School of Education and Information Science Los Angeles, CA	To transcribe interviews with UCLA graduate history students	10/12/99	\$2,500
University of Cape Town Fund, Inc. New York, NY	To support local expenses related to a preservation workshop in Cape Town, South Africa	11/30/99	\$10,000
University of Illinois Champaign, IL	To support the development of a report on humanities scholars' use of electronic resources	8/27/99	\$10,000
University of Minnesota Minneapolis, MN	To support a study on the theory of cost allocation for information resources	7/18/97	\$25,000

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

**FINANCIAL STATEMENTS
WITH
ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

**FOR THE YEAR ENDED JUNE 30, 2001
(With Summarized Financial Information for June 30, 2000)**

**WITH
INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT**

**STONE AND SPRING
Certified Public Accountants
Herndon, Virginia**

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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INDEPENDENT AUDITORS' REPORT

To the Board of Trustees
Council on Library and Information Resources
Washington, D.C.

We have audited the accompanying statement of financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2001, and the related statements of activities and changes in net assets, and cash flows for the year then ended. These financial statements are the responsibility of the Council's management. Our responsibility is to express an opinion on these financial statements based on our audit.

We conducted our audit in accordance with auditing standards generally accepted in the United States of America. Those standards require that we plan and perform the audit to obtain reasonable assurance about whether the financial statements are free of material misstatement. An audit includes examining, on a test basis, evidence supporting the amounts and disclosures in the financial statements. An audit also includes assessing the accounting principles used and significant estimates made by management, as well as evaluating the overall financial statement presentation. We believe that our audit provides a reasonable basis for our opinion.

In our opinion, the financial statements referred to above present fairly, in all material respects, the financial position of the Council on Library and Information Resources as of June 30, 2001, and the changes in its net assets and its cash flows for the year then ended in conformity with accounting principles generally accepted in the United States of America.

Our audit was conducted for the purpose of forming an opinion on the basic financial statements taken as a whole. The accompanying schedule of functional expenses is presented for purposes of additional analysis and is not a required part of the basic financial statements. Such information has been subjected to the auditing procedures applied in the audit of the basic financial statements and, in our opinion, is fairly stated in all material respects in relation to the basic financial statements taken as a whole.

Certified Public Accountants

Herndon, Virginia
August 13, 2001

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF FINANCIAL POSITION

June 30, 2001

(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2000)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	Temporarily <u>Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2001</u>	<u>Total 2000</u>
Assets				
Cash and cash equivalents	\$ 689,245	\$ -	\$ 689,245	\$ 573,110
Investments	793,573	5,551,537	6,345,110	5,447,852
Accounts receivable	-	-	-	21,000
Furniture and equipment, net	54,525	-	54,525	34,636
Other assets	<u>26,769</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>26,769</u>	<u>33,820</u>
Total Assets	<u>\$ 1,564,112</u>	<u>\$ 5,551,537</u>	<u>\$ 7,115,649</u>	<u>\$ 6,110,418</u>
Liabilities and Net Assets				
Accounts payable and accrued expenses	\$ 301,884	\$ 171,374	\$ 473,258	\$ 352,031
Capital lease payable	2,510	-	2,510	5,140
Sublet deposits	<u>2,956</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>2,956</u>	<u>2,956</u>
Total Liabilities	<u>\$ 307,350</u>	<u>\$ 171,374</u>	<u>\$ 478,724</u>	<u>\$ 360,127</u>
Net Assets	<u>1,256,762</u>	<u>5,380,163</u>	<u>6,636,925</u>	<u>5,750,291</u>
Total Liabilities and Net Assets	<u>\$ 1,564,112</u>	<u>\$ 5,551,537</u>	<u>\$ 7,115,649</u>	<u>\$ 6,110,418</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
STATEMENT OF ACTIVITIES AND CHANGES IN NET ASSETS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2001
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2000)

	<u>Unrestricted</u>	<u>Temporarily Restricted</u>	<u>Total 2001</u>	<u>Total 2000</u>
Revenue				
Grants and contracts	\$ 49,257	\$ 1,444,007	\$ 1,493,264	\$ 3,514,559
Contributions	434,953	1,304,917	1,739,870	1,083,944
Publication sales	14,238	-	14,238	31,312
Investment income	34,149	231,803	265,952	212,049
Other income	<u>11,890</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>11,890</u>	<u>31,951</u>
	<u>\$ 544,487</u>	<u>\$ 2,980,727</u>	<u>\$ 3,525,214</u>	<u>\$ 4,873,815</u>
Net Assets released from Restrictions				
Satisfaction of program restrictions	<u>\$ 2,103,333</u>	<u>\$ (2,103,333)</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ -</u>
Total Revenue	<u>\$ 2,647,820</u>	<u>\$ 877,394</u>	<u>\$ 3,525,214</u>	<u>\$ 4,873,815</u>
Expenses				
Program services:				
Preservation	\$ 807,306	\$ -	\$ 807,468	\$ 1,009,119
Leadership	482,443	-	482,443	398,891
Digital libraries	669,746	-	669,746	522,535
Resources for scholarship	98,374	-	98,374	42,982
Economics of information	<u>49,369</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>49,369</u>	<u>24,596</u>
Total Program Services	<u>\$ 2,107,238</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 2,107,238</u>	<u>\$ 1,998,123</u>
Administration	<u>531,342</u>	<u>-</u>	<u>531,342</u>	<u>385,701</u>
Total Expenses	<u>\$ 2,638,580</u>	<u>\$ -</u>	<u>\$ 2,638,580</u>	<u>\$ 2,383,824</u>
Change in Net Assets	9,240	877,394	886,634	2,489,991
Net Assets, Beginning of Year	<u>1,247,522</u>	<u>4,502,769</u>	<u>5,750,291</u>	<u>3,260,300</u>
Net Assets, End of Year	<u>\$ 1,256,762</u>	<u>\$ 5,380,163</u>	<u>\$ 6,636,925</u>	<u>\$ 5,750,291</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

STATEMENT OF CASH FLOWS

For the Year Ended June 30, 2001
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2000)

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2000</u>
Operating Activities		
Change in net assets	\$ 886,634	\$ 2,489,991
Adjustments to reconcile change in net assets to net cash provided by (used) in operating activities		
Depreciation	23,116	26,299
(Increase) decrease in other assets	7,051	(6,259)
(Increase) decrease in accounts receivable	21,000	(21,000)
Increase (decrease) in accounts payable and accrued expenses	<u>121,227</u>	<u>109,186</u>
Net Cash Provided (Used) By Operating Activities	<u>\$ 1,059,028</u>	<u>\$ 2,598,217</u>
Investing Activities		
Proceeds from sales of investments	\$ 8,995,667	\$ 12,021,918
Purchases of investments	(9,892,925)	(14,499,530)
Purchases of furniture and equipment	<u>(43,005)</u>	<u>(26,744)</u>
Net Cash Provided (Used) By Investing Activities	<u>\$ (940,263)</u>	<u>\$ (2,504,356)</u>
Financing Activities		
Principal payments on capital lease	\$ <u>(2,630)</u>	\$ <u>(2,631)</u>
Net Cash Provided (used) By Financing Activities	<u>\$ (2,630)</u>	<u>\$ (2,631)</u>
Net Change in Cash and Cash Equivalents	\$ 116,135	\$ 91,230
Cash and cash equivalents, beginning of year	<u>573,110</u>	<u>481,880</u>
Cash and cash equivalents, end of year	<u>\$ 689,245</u>	<u>\$ 573,110</u>
Supplemental Cash Flow Information		
Interest paid during the year	\$ <u>668</u>	\$ <u>722</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2001

NOTE 1- Organization

The Council is a not-for-profit organization incorporated under the laws of the District of Columbia in 1988 for the purpose of fostering, developing, and supporting systematic and purposeful collaboration in order to ensure the preservation of the published and documentary record in all formats and provide equitable access to that information.

The Council's operations are financed through contributions from colleges, universities and other organizations and through general support grants and restricted grants from private foundations and other sources. The Council conducts its work directly through committees and working groups as well as through contracts with other organizations and individuals.

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies

Basis of accounting - The accompanying financial statements of the Council have been prepared on the accrual basis.

Grant revenue and recognition of grantor restrictions - The Council reports grants as temporarily restricted support if they are received with grantor stipulations that limit the use of the grants as to time or purpose. When either condition is satisfied, temporarily restricted net assets are reclassified to unrestricted net assets and reported in the statement of activities and changes in net assets as net assets released from restrictions. Support that is restricted by the grantor is reported as an increase in unrestricted net assets if the restriction expires in the reporting period in which the support is recognized.

Contracts / Grants payable - Contracts made by the Council are recorded as contracts payable and expensed at the time contracts are awarded. Current period expenses are adjusted for contract refunds or over appropriations when received.

Board designated net assets - From time to time, the Board of Trustees designates a portion of unrestricted net assets for various short-term projects.

Cash and cash equivalents - For purposes of the statement of cash flows, cash and cash equivalents consist primarily of deposits in a money market account and investments with original maturities of 90 days or less.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2001

(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Functional allocation of expenses - Costs of the various programs have been summarized on a functional basis in the accompanying financial statements. Certain indirect costs which include rent and other expenses are identified as support services costs and have been allocated directly to programs and administration. Salaries and travel costs have been allocated directly to programs and administration on a time-allocated basis.

Furniture and Equipment - Furniture and equipment are recorded at cost, less accumulated depreciation. Depreciation expense is computed using the straight-line method over the estimated useful lives of the respective assets. Expenditures for maintenance and repairs are charged against income as incurred; betterments which increase the value or materially extend the life of the related assets are capitalized.

Contributions - The Council records grant income as unrestricted, temporarily restricted, or permanently restricted support, depending upon the terms and conditions of the grant.

Fair value of financial instruments - Management estimates that the fair value of all financial instruments at June 30, 2001 does not differ materially from the aggregate carrying values reported in the accompanying statement of financial position due to the short term maturities of those instruments.

Use of estimates - The preparation of financial statements in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles requires management to make estimates and assumptions that affect the reported amounts of assets and liabilities and disclosure of contingent assets and liabilities at the date of the financial statements. Estimates also affect the reported amounts of revenues and expenses during the reporting period. Actual results could differ from those estimates.

Summarized financial information - The financial statements include certain prior year comparative information summarized in total but not by net asset class. Such information does not include sufficient detail to constitute a presentation in conformity with generally accepted accounting principles. Accordingly, such information should be read in conjunction with the Council's financial statements for the year ended June 30, 2000 from which the summarized information was derived.

Reclassification of prior year information - Certain amounts from the prior year have been reclassified to enhance comparability.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30,2001

(Continued)

NOTE 2- Summary of Significant Accounting Policies (continued)

Investments - The Organization has adopted SFAS No. 124, "Accounting for Certain Investments Held by Not-for-Profit Organizations". Under SFAS No. 124, investments in marketable securities with readily determinable fair values and all investments in debt securities are reported at their fair values in the statement of financial position. Unrealized gains and losses are included in the change in net assets. Investment income and gains restricted by a donor are reported as increases in unrestricted net assets if the restrictions are met (either by passage of time or by use) in the reporting period in which the income and gains are recognized.

Investment return consists of the following at June 30, 2001

	Gain/loss on <u>Investments</u>	Unrealized Gain/(loss) on <u>Investments</u>	<u>Fair Value</u>
Stocks	\$ 8,423	\$ (8,189)	\$ 78,728
Corporate fixed income	216,511	44,163	3,515,267
Government securities	32,040	-	-
Certificate of Deposit	10,021	-	195,000
Mutual funds	<u>105,068</u>	<u>(160,898)</u>	<u>2,556,115</u>
Subtotal	\$ 372,063	\$ (124,924)	\$ <u>6,345,110</u>
Cash and cash equivalents	<u>18,813</u>	-	\$ <u>689,245</u>
Total	\$ <u>390,876</u>	\$ <u>(124,924)</u>	

NOTE 3 - Income Taxes

The Council is exempt from federal income taxes under Section 501(c)(3) of the Internal Revenue Code and applicable regulations of the District of Columbia.

NOTE 4 - Furniture and Equipment

Furniture and equipment consist of the following:

	<u>2001</u>	<u>2000</u>
Furniture and equipment	\$ 134,334	\$ 140,275
Leasehold improvements	<u>4,015</u>	<u>4,015</u>
	138,349	144,290
Less: accumulated depreciation and amortization	<u>(83,824)</u>	<u>(109,654)</u>
	\$ <u>54,525</u>	\$ <u>34,636</u>

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

NOTES TO FINANCIAL STATEMENTS

June 30, 2001
(Concluded)

NOTE 5 - Net Assets released from Restrictions

Net assets were released from grantor restrictions by incurring expenses satisfying the restricted purposes or by occurrence of other events specified by grantors.

NOTE 6 - Retirement Plan

Employees are eligible for participation in the Council's defined contribution retirement annuity program ("the Plan") administered through the TIAA/CREF insurance companies. Individual contracts issued under the Plan provide for full and immediate vesting of the Council's contributions. The Council contributes 15% of employees' salaries to the Plan each year. The Council's contributions were \$116,525 and \$109,300 in 2001 and 2000, respectively.

NOTE 7 - Concentrations of Credit Risk

Financial instruments which potentially subject the Council to concentrations of credit risk consist primarily of cash equivalents. At June 30, 2001 and 2000, approximately \$124,553 and \$310,635 respectively, in cash equivalents was being held by a third party in a money market account that invests solely in United States government securities. This amount is not insured by the Federal Deposit Insurance Corporation. In addition, cash in the bank at June 30, 2001 and 2000 exceeded FDIC insurance limits by approximately \$527,012 and \$168,044. Furthermore, all balances in investment accounts are uninsured.

NOTE 8 - Commitments

The Council has entered into a noncancelable operating lease agreement for its office space which expires in August, 2003. The Council is subleasing a portion of its space until August, 2003. The Council is also leasing a phone system at a cost of \$13,150 which has been classified as a capital lease.

Future minimum payments under all leases, net of sublease receipts, are as follows:

Year Ending June 30,	Capital Lease	Operating Lease
2002	\$ 3,352	\$ 142,149
2003	-	144,348
Thereafter	-	24,166
Total	<u>\$ 3,352</u>	<u>\$ 310,663</u>
Amount representing interest	<u>842</u>	
Present value of Net Minimum Lease payments	<u>\$ 2,510</u>	

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES
SCHEDULE OF FUNCTIONAL EXPENSES

For the Year Ended June 30, 2001
(With summarized financial information for June 30, 2000)

	Digital Libraries	Economics of Information	Leadership	Preservation	Resources For Scholarship	Program Services	Admin.	Total 2001	Total 2000
	\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	\$	\$
Grants	-	-	8,000	10,000	-	18,000	-	18,000	31,311
Refunds	-	(15,000)	-	-	-	(15,000)	(10,000)	(25,000)	(11,518)
Contracts	12,296	10,000	58,400	211	19,900	100,807	25,000	125,807	408,694
Meeting & Travel	216,653	1,424	239,852	93,085	44,970	595,984	35,029	631,013	427,978
Project Expenditures	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	67,839
Communications	20,113	27,782	7,537	14,679	24,668	94,779	20,620	115,399	115,552
Staff	374,980	24,900	74,570	640,115	8,250	1,122,815	188,195	1,311,010	961,412
Consultants	23,891	-	13,430	38,087	275	75,683	32,848	108,531	69,903
Program Support	21,813	263	80,654	11,129	311	114,170	214,749	328,919	288,999
Board Expense	-	-	-	-	-	-	24,901	24,901	23,654
TOTAL	<u>\$ 669,746</u>	<u>\$ 49,369</u>	<u>\$ 482,443</u>	<u>\$ 807,306</u>	<u>\$ 98,374</u>	<u>\$ 2,107,238</u>	<u>\$ 531,342</u>	<u>\$ 2,638,580</u>	<u>\$ 2,383,824</u>

The accompanying notes to financial statements are an integral part of this statement.

COUNCIL ON LIBRARY AND INFORMATION RESOURCES

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